

EVOLVING TRENDS IN CULTIVATING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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Abstract. *In an increasingly globalized world, the ability to communicate effectively in multiple languages has become a valuable asset. As such, foreign language teaching has evolved to prioritize the development of communicative competence—the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in various contexts. This article explores the current trends shaping the development of communicative competence in the process of teaching foreign languages.*

Keywords: *Communicative competence, foreign language teaching, technology integration, task-based learning, CLIL, intercultural competence, authentic communication.*

Аннотация. *В условиях растущей глобализации мира способность эффективно общаться на нескольких языках стала ценным активом. Таким образом, в преподавании иностранного языка приоритет отдается развитию коммуникативной компетентности – способности правильно и эффективно использовать язык в различных контекстах. В данной статье исследуются современные тенденции, формирующие развитие коммуникативной компетентности в процессе обучения иностранным языкам.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативная компетентность, обучение иностранному языку, интеграция технологий, целевое обучение, CLIL, межкультурная компетентность, аутентичная коммуникация.*

Annotatsiya. *Globalashib borayotgan dunyoda bir nechta tillarda samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyati qimmatli boylikka aylandi. Shunday qilib, chet tillarini o'rgatish kommunikativ kompetentsiyani - tildan turli kontekstlarda to'g'ri va samarali foydalanish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga ustuvor ahamiyat berish uchun rivojlandi. Ushbu maqola chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishning hozirgi tendentsiyalarini o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Kommunikativ kompetentsiya, chet tillarini o'rgatish, texnologiya integratsiyasi, vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim, CLIL, madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya, haqiqiy muloqot.*

Language teaching in the 21st century encounters a myriad of challenges stemming from technological advancements, evolving communication dynamics, diverse learner demographics, and shifting educational paradigms. This article examines the actual problems faced by language educators today and explores potential strategies to address them. It delves into the impact of technology on language instruction, the necessity of incorporating cultural competence, the demand for flexible and adaptive teaching methodologies, and the role of assessment in measuring language proficiency. By recognizing and effectively responding to these challenges, language educators can navigate the complexities of language teaching in the modern era and empower learners for success in a globalized world. This era presents both unprecedented opportunities and challenges for language educators worldwide. With the rapid development of digital technologies, language teaching has been revolutionized, offering innovative tools and platforms for instruction, practice, and assessment (Hinkel, 2012). However, this digital transformation also brings about the need for educators to adapt their teaching methods to effectively integrate technology into the language learning process. Moreover, the increasingly interconnected global society demands

language learners not only acquire linguistic proficiency but also develop intercultural competence to effectively communicate and collaborate across cultures. As such, language teaching in the 21st century emphasizes the importance of incorporating cultural content, real-world contexts, and authentic materials into the curriculum to provide learners with meaningful language learning experiences. Furthermore, the diverse backgrounds and learning needs of students in today's classrooms require language educators to employ flexible and inclusive teaching approaches that cater to individual differences. Differentiated instruction, personalized learning pathways, and adaptive assessment strategies are essential components of effective language teaching in the 21st-century classroom. Hawkins and Norton (2009, as cited in Waller et al., 2017) suggested five principles of critical teaching, which cover all crucial aspects of teaching. The first is “the situated nature of programs and practice,” which focuses on the students' cultural backgrounds and teaching methods. The relationship between teachers and students determines responsiveness to learners and dialogic involvement. I believe that if teachers are too severe, students will become unmotivated and stop contributing to class discussions. Cooperation is an excellent method to engage every student in the class and provide them with a chance to contribute. The third concept is reflexivity, which states that educators should constantly evaluate their backgrounds, experiences, and teaching philosophies in order to determine how they can continue to grow.

Cultural competence in language teaching refers to the ability of educators to effectively integrate cultural awareness, understanding, and sensitivity into language instruction (Richards, 2003). It involves acknowledging and respecting the diverse cultural backgrounds of learners, and fostering an inclusive learning environment where students feel valued and respected. Cultural competence in language teaching goes beyond simply teaching vocabulary and grammar; it encompasses an understanding of the cultural norms, values, beliefs, and practices associated with the target language. Educators strive to help students develop intercultural communicative competence, which enables them to interact effectively and appropriately with speakers of the target language in various cultural contexts. Cultural competence in language teaching is essential for preparing students to communicate effectively and respectfully in a multicultural and interconnected world. It enhances language learning outcomes and promotes intercultural understanding and cooperation.

Language teaching methodologies encompass a wide range of approaches, techniques, and strategies used by educators to facilitate the teaching and learning of languages. These methodologies are continuously evolving in response to advancements in educational research, technological innovations, and changing educational needs. Some common language teaching methodologies include:

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is focused on developing students' communicative competence through meaningful interaction and real-life communication tasks. CLT emphasizes the use of authentic language materials and activities that simulate real-world language use (Savignon, 1991).

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) involves designing classroom tasks that require learners to use the target language to accomplish specific goals or tasks. TBLT aims to promote language learning through authentic and purposeful language use, with a focus on fluency and practical language skills (Moore, 2018).

Audio-Lingual Method (ALM) is based on the principles of behaviorism, this method emphasizes the repetitive practice of language patterns through drills and exercises. It focuses on developing students' oral proficiency and automaticity in using the target language (Rilling, 2018).

Direct Method advocates for teaching language directly through the target language, without the use of translation. It emphasizes the use of visual aids, realia, and gestures to convey meaning, and encourages students to learn through context and immersion (Benati, 2018)

Grammar-Translation Method (GTM) focuses on the explicit teaching of grammar rules and the translation of texts between the target language and the native language. It places a strong emphasis on accuracy and written language skills (Benati, 2018).

Content-Based Instruction (CBI) integrates language learning with content-based subjects such as science, history, or literature. CBI aims to develop both language proficiency and content knowledge simultaneously, making language learning more meaningful and relevant for students.

The Natural Approach based on the principles of naturalistic language acquisition, this approach emphasizes the use of meaningful input and a supportive language environment to facilitate language learning. It encourages students to acquire language through exposure and immersion, similar to the way children learn their first language. These are just a few examples of language teaching methodologies, and educators often combine elements from different approaches to create a tailored approach that meets the needs of their students and learning objectives. Additionally, with the advancement of technology, digital tools and online resources are increasingly being integrated into language teaching methodologies to enhance learning outcomes and engage students in meaningful language practice.

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In the 21st century, assessment strategies in language teaching have evolved to align with the changing landscape of education and the demands of a globalized world. There are different assessment strategies, such as technology-enhanced assessment. Integrating technology into assessment practices allows for more dynamic and interactive assessments. Online platforms, multimedia presentations, digital portfolios, and computer-adaptive tests can provide more authentic and engaging assessment experiences for students. The next type of assessment is performance-based assessment. Emphasizing performance-based assessments that measure students' ability to apply language skills in real-world contexts. Tasks such as presentations, role-plays, debates, and collaborative projects assess not only language proficiency but also communication and critical thinking skills. We can also consider task-based assessment, cultural-competence assessment, task-based assessment, etc. By leveraging these assessment strategies, language teachers can effectively evaluate students' language proficiency, promote deeper learning, and prepare students to thrive in the multilingual and multicultural world of the 21st century.

In conclusion, language teaching in the 21st century is characterized by the integration of technology, emphasis on intercultural competence, and implementation of flexible and inclusive pedagogical practices. By embracing these trends and addressing the challenges they entail, language educators can prepare students to thrive in an increasingly interconnected and multicultural world.

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